

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON FUTURES AND OPTIONS TRADERS IN BIDAR CITY

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ABSTRACT

The research paper focuses on the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on Futures and Option Traders. In order to achieve this objective survey was conducted using Google form consisting structured questionnaire, same is shared among 119 Future & Option traders, who constitute the sample and were active in Future and Option trading in Bidar city. Following were the aspects that were considered for the study. Socio-economic profile of Futures and Options traders, the impact of covid-19 pandemic on futures and option traders and their level of satisfaction in returns earned in Futures and option trading. Level of satisfaction in Futures and options trading is considered as Dependent variable and gender, age, education, occupation and annual income are considered as Independent Variables. Data collected were analyzed by using SPSS version 25, following analysis were performed. Descriptive statistics: Mean, Standard Deviation and (one way) ANOVA was used to test the Hypothesis. The results of the study revealed that Majority of traders booked loss during Covid-19 market crash and faced margin adjustment problems and it affected their trading frequency too. But best part is majority of traders have recovered their losses when market recovered, but their trading frequency has decreased post Covid-19. Majority of Traders are satisfied with the returns earned in F&O segment in Bidar City.

Key words: Futures and options, Covid-19, traders, satisfaction

INTRODUCION:

Covid -19 pandemic created a spike in volatility in stock market trading activity, which has quickly spread across the globe. The S&P index fell by 20% within 3 weeks and consistently continued to decline by 30% in a record 30 days. On 9th March, Sensex crashed by 1,941.67 points and Nifty-50 came down by 538 points. Covid-19 outbreak has created havoc all over the globe and in India too (Wikipedia, n.d.).(Mirjana Dobric April 8, n.d.) As per history stock market crashes are common, it is very difficult to forecast the stock market. Covid-19 pandemic has impacted the stock market most severely but for shorter period. Following international markets were also crashed; the US stock market was also crashed. Dow, S&P 500, and Nasdaq

were dropped by 30%. On March 12th 2020 all three markets managed the crisis by elevating , Dow Jones 76.05%, S&P 500 76.12 and Nasdaq 94.99%.The Covid-19 pandemic was a harsh teacher for the investor, the investors must follow the situation on a daily basis.

BIDAR CITY PROFILE

Bidar city is situated in north eastern part of Karnataka state in India, which borders Maharashtra and Telengana. The city is famous for many sites of architectural. The total population 214,373(constitutes male: 110628 & Female:103745) and literates 161,094 (Male:87,828 and Female:73,266)(*Bidar Population*, n.d.)

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the socio-economic profile of futures and options traders in Bidar City.
2. To know the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on Futures and Options traders.
3. To assess the traders level of satisfaction in Futures and Options trading.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Covid-19 turned out to be the black swan event which became a real-life stress test for the Futures and Options Market(Eurex, 2021).These crisis have erupted in tremendous (Covid induced economic uncertainties) The infectious disease was considerable which directly affected stock market globally (Liu et al., 2020). Covid -19 has impacted financial market dramatically. It affected the world economy and India, everything came to halt due to lock down order in India(Alam et al., 2020). 41 days lockdown in India which affected manufacturing ,supply chains and economy of the country(Agrawal et al., 2020). Fear & uncertainty prevails in the market all over the world. (Kumar & Kumara, 2020).The covid-19 has affected exchange rates and international capital cycles. There was extreme volatility in financial market (Afrina et al., 2020). It jeopardized developed or developing economies no matter large or small, this pandemic remains uncertain till today (Barua, 2021). Huge volatility were found in global market due to carona virus (DayongZhangaMinHuaQiangJibc et al., n.d.). The bearish market were ensuing (Conlon & McGee, 2020).It is a long term challenge to improving our ability to respond to outbreaks(DayongZhangaMinHuaQiangJibc et al., n.d.) Sentiments which are Country-specific affect the share price movements (*Froot and Dabora 1998.Pdf*, n.d.). The investors risk and return expectations have changed, which is leading them to reframe their portfolios. Most of the Investors are moving towards conservative portfolios (Himanshu et al., 2021). Indian investors are aware about portfolio allotments and risk and return of their investment(Bhaskaran & Arts, 2014). The investors investment priority is based on several factors like his/her awareness environment, level of exposure, intensions, beliefs, responsibilities and so on.(Umamaheswari & Kumar, 2014). Still individual investors prefer risk free investment (Gates, n.d.).The volatility of market unpredictable

(Sultana, 2010). The individual investors' expectations and beliefs are different which affects prices and returns (Barberis et al., 2005). Investors sentiment affect investment decisions and stock prices (Marinč, 2016). Risk tolerance depends upon gender, single males are high risk takers than married males, unmarried females and married females (Yao & Hanna, n.d.)

RESEARCH METHODS

The research design for this study is descriptive in nature. Data collected from primary and secondary source. Primary data was collected through Google form from Futures and Options traders in Bidar city. The Google form consists of two sections measuring demographic variables and covid-19 Impact on their trading.

Duration of study: Lockdown was imposed in India from 24th March 2020 to 31st May 2020 in four phases, so the duration of this particular study was extended till 15th June 2020.

Population & Sample size: The population consists of investors trading in Futures and Options segment in Bidar City and total population was 170. www.openepi.com sample size calculator was used to calculate sample size. Based on the output of sample size calculator sample size was chosen as 119. Secondary data was collected from published reports by derivative market, stock market website in India.

Data Analysis: SPSS version 25 software was used for analysis. Descriptive statistics and One way ANOVA was used to test the hypothesis

Table:01 Gender wise classification of F&O Traders

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	83	69.7
Female	36	30.3
Total	119	100

The figure: 01 shows that from total sample of 119 in Bidar city, 69.7% respondents are male traders and 30.3% are female traders.

Figure :01 Gender wise classification of F&O Traders

H0a: There is no significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading between male and female.

H1a: There is a significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading between male and female.

One way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) test was conducted to compare means of level of satisfaction in F&O trading variables for two different groups of respondents, that is male and female traders and the results exhibit in table: 1.1

Table:1.1 Mean, SD and f value for gender

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	F	P value
Level of satisfaction in F&O trading	Male	83	3.83	1.091	12.220	0.001
	Female	36	4.53	0.736		

As the result shows that P value is <0.005 there is a significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading between male and female gender the null hypothesis H0a is rejected and alternative hypothesis H1a is accepted.

Table:02 Age wise classification of F&O Traders

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 25 years	17	14.3
26-35	51	42.9
36-45	30	25.2
46-55	11	9.2
56 and above	10	8.4

Total	119	100.0
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The figure:02 shows that from total sample of 119 in Bidar city , Majority of traders belong to age group of 26-35 year that is 42.9% followed by 36-45 that is 25.2% and least are from the age group of 56 and above years that is 8.4%

Figure: 02 Age wise classification of F&O Traders

H0b: There is no significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with age group

H1b: There is a significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with age group

One way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) test was conducted to test the significant relationship between the level of satisfaction in F&O trading with age group and the results manifest in table: 2.1

Table:2.1 Mean,SD and f value for Age group

Variable	Age group	N	Mean	SD	F	P value
Level of satisfaction	Below 25	17	4.35	8.862	0.782	0.539
	26-35	51	4.08	1.093		
	36-45	30	3.90	0.885		

in F&O	46-55	11	3.73	1.272		
trading	56 and Above	10	4.10	1.287		

As P value is >0.05 the result proves that there is no significant difference between the level of satisfaction in F&O trading with age group H0b is accepted

Table: 03 Education wise classification of F&O Traders

Education	Frequency	Percentage
Below Bachelor Degree	26	21.8
Above Bachelor Degree	93	78.2
Total	119	100.0

Figure: 03 shows that maximum F&O traders are above Bachelor Degree

Figure: 03 Education wise classification of F&O Traders

H0c: There is no significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with Education

H1c: There is no significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with Education

One way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) test was conducted to test the significant relationship between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with education and the results exhibit in table: 3.1

Table: 3.1 Mean, SD and f value for Education

Variable	Education	N	Mean	SD	F	P value
Level of satisfaction in F&O trading	Below Bachelor Degree	26	4.35	0.745	2.864	0.093
	Above Bachelor Degree	93	3.96	1.103		

As P value is >0.05 there is no significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with Education null hypothesis is H_0 is accepted

Table:04 Occupation wise classification of F&O Traders

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Student	17	14.3
Professional	51	42.9
Service	30	25.2
Self employed	11	9.2
House wife	10	8.4
Total	119	100.0

The figure: 07 shows that from total sample of 119 Maximum F&O traders are Professional 42.9% followed by Service 25.2% and students 14.3% least are house wife 8.4%.

Figure: 04 Occupation wise classification of F&O Traders

H0d: There is no significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with Occupation

H1d: There is a significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with Occupation

One way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) test was conducted to test the significant relationship between the level of satisfaction in F&O trading with occupation and the results appeared in table: 4.1

Table:4.1 Mean ,SD and f value for occupation

Variable	Occupation	N	Mean	SD	F	P value
Level of satisfaction in F&O trading	Student	16	4.13	0.806	1.053	0.390
	Professional	40	4.08	0.888		
	Service	21	3.67	1.354		
	Self employed	29	4.24	1.091		
	Retired	9	3.78	1.202		

	House wife	4	4.50	0.577		
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As P value is >0.05 it is proved that there is no significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with occupation null hypothesis is H0d is accepted

Table: 5 Annual Income wise classification of F&O Traders

Income	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 2 Lakhs	31	26.1
2-3	30	25.2
3-4	24	20.2
Above 4 Lakhs	34	28.6
Total	119	100.0

The figure:05 shows that Maximum F&O traders are having Annual income above 4 lakhs that is 28.6% followed by less than 2 lakhs that is 26.1% and 2-3 lakhs 25.2% and lowest is 3-4 lakhs 20.2%.

Figure: 05 Annual Income wise classification of F&O Traders

H0d: there is no significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with Annual Income

H1d: there is a significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with Annual Income

An one way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) test was conducted to test the significant relationship between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with Annual Income and the results manifest in table: 5.1

Table:5.1 Mean ,SD and f value for Annual Income

Variable	Annual Income	N	Mean	SD	F	P value
Level of satisfaction in F&O trading	Less than 2 Lakhs	31	4.06	1.15	0.063	0.979
	2-3	30	4.07	1.14		
	3-4	24	3.96	0.859		
	Above 4 lakhs	34	4.06	1.013		

As P value is >0.05 it is proved that there is no significant difference between level of satisfaction in F&O trading with Annual Income null hypothesis is H_0 is accepted.

Table:6 Impact of covid-19 on F&O traders

variable	Covid-19 affected trading	Losses booked during covid-19 market crash	Faced margin adjusting problem during covid-19 market crash	Losses recovered post Covid-19 recovered
Yes	85.6%	84.0%	86.6%	58.0%
No	14.4%	16.0%	13.4%	42.0%

Figure:06 Impact of covid-19 on F&O traders

The above Figure:06 depicts that Covid-19 pandemic has affected 85.6% F&O traders in Bidar City and 84.0% traders have booked losses during covid-19 stock market correction, 86.6% traders faced problem of margin adjustment problem and 58.0% traders have recovered their losses post covid-19 and 42.0% traders have not yet recovered their losses.

Table:7 Comparison of frequency of trading pre and post covid-19

Variables	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Occasionally
Frequency of before covid-19	29%	18%	15%	56%
Frequency of trading in post-covid-19	21%	8.4%	8.4%	62.2%

Figure: 07 Comparison of frequency of trading pre and post covid-19

The above figure shows the comparison of trading frequency of F&O traders pre and post covid-19. As per the graph 29% of traders used to trade daily followed by 18% weekly and 56% occasionally where as post covid-19 21% of traders are trading daily followed by 8.4% weekly and 62.2% traders are trading occasionally. Hence it is clear from the graph that trading frequency has decreased post covid-19.

Table: 8 Level of satisfaction on returns earned in F&O segment

	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	3	2.5
Disagree	10	8.4
Strongly disagree nor Disagree	14	11.8
Agree	44	37.0
Strongly Agree	48	40.3

Figure: 08 Level of satisfaction on returns earned in F&O segment

The above graph shows that 40.3% F&O traders are satisfied with returns earned from F&O trading followed by 37% only 2.5% traders are not satisfied with their returns.

RESEARCH RESULTS

1. It is revealed from the study that majority of the respondents trading in F&O segment are male traders. This indicates that F&O trading is more popular among males than females.
2. It is found that traders within age group of 26-35 year constitute the major proportion of F&O traders. It is also found that level of satisfaction is not based on age.
3. The study shows that traders having above Bachelor degree are more interested in trading than below Bachelor degree.
4. It is found that the education does not influence their level of satisfaction in F&O trading.
5. The study reveals that majority of F&O traders are Professionals. It is also found that occupation does not influence the level of satisfaction in F&O trading.
6. It is found that majority of traders having income more than 4 lakhs and above per annum are trading in F&O segment.
7. The study shows that Covid-19 pandemic has affected 85.6% F&O traders in Bidar City and 84.0% traders have booked losses during covid-19 stock market correction, 86.6% traders faced problem of margin adjustment problem and 58.0% traders have recovered their losses post covid-19 and 42.0% traders have not yet recovered their losses.
8. When the trading frequency was compared with pre and post covid-19, it is found from figure-07 that during pre Covid-19, 29% of traders used to trade daily followed by 18% weekly and 56% occasionally where as post covid-19 21% of traders are trading daily followed by 8.4% Weekly and 62.2% traders are trading occasionally. Hence it is clear that trading frequency has decreased post covid-19.

9. With reference to the table:8 in the study period it is found that 40.3% of F&O traders are highly satisfied and 37% are satisfied with returns earned in F&O segment.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded from the study that Covid-19 pandemic has severely impacted F&O traders in Bidar city. Majority of traders booked loss during Covid-19 market crash and faced margin adjustment problems and it affected their trading frequency too. But best part is majority of traders have recovered their losses when market recovered, but their trading frequency has decreased post Covid-19. Majority of Traders are satisfied with the returns earned in F&O segment in Bidar City.

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